

INTIMATE PARTNER VIOLENCE AND EXTRAMARITAL AFFAIRS IN UYO URBAN, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

Queen Edopese Enyina

Department of Sociology and Anthropology
University of Uyo, Uyo
queenenyina@gmail.com, 08169917915

Lucky O. Abogoh

Department of Sociological Foundation of Education
University of Uyo, Uyo
luckyabogoh@uniuyo.edu.ng, 07064968893

Abstract

Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) is one of the most prevalent social problems in Uyo Urban, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria as cases continue to rise very rapidly in the area. This study therefore was to ascertain if intimate partner violence can give rise to deviant sexual acts like extramarital affairs. It adopted the differential association theory for theoretical framework. Participants in the study were purposively drawn using a snowball sampling technique while data were obtained through interview of participants and key informants. Data analysis was done qualitatively as responses from participants were grouped in themes according to the study specific objectives. Results indicated that intimate partner violence contributes to deviant sexual acts like extramarital affairs in the study area. It was also found that the most dominant form of IPV in the area is physical abuse (punching, slapping, and shoving) and married women were the most abused set of people in the study area. To address the high prevalence of IPV, punishments of offenders in accordance with the law should be enforced to serve as deterrence to others and also encourage "silent victims" to speak-up and call for help. In addition, couple should be enlighten on the dangers IPV which lead to extra-marital affairs.

Keywords: Intimate Partner Violence (IPV), extra-marital affairs, deviant and Uyo

Introduction

History is dotted with many records and forms of violence, including Intimate Partner Violence (IPV). For example, the code of Hammurabi, a set of 282 laws that the ancient monarch Hammurabi employed to administer Babylon between 1750 and 1792 B.C.E., is seen as the oldest written law that is known to exist. In Hammurabi's code, there were severe penalties for crimes. For instance, a false allegation of someone engaging in incest was punishable by death. The common saying "an eye for an eye" was directly influenced by the harsh punishments imposed by this legal code, which meant that any harm, like the loss of an eye, had to be made up for by a similar sentence. Nevertheless, those laws were only in place for men. Women and children had a tougher time because they were seen as property under this rule. They were not protected by the law, and in some cases, Hammurabi's code required males to use violence against their wives and children. A woman's husband was permitted to

tie her up and drown her if she was found having an adulterous engagement outside the marriage, thus encouraging Intimate Partner Violence. According to Encyclopaedia Britannica, Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) refers to behaviour within an intimate relationship that causes physical, sexual, or psychological harm, including acts of aggression, sexual coercion, psychological abuse, and controlling behaviours (Effah-Chukwuma, Ukommi, and Bassey, 2022).

IPV could be measured as Physical Violence, Sexual Violence, and Emotional Violence. Contrary to popular belief, physical abuse in relationships is a serious and widespread problem. It is also tragic and drastically changes lives. Although physical abuse is the most obvious type, it rarely occurs in a relationship when there isn't verbal or emotional abuse present. However, a relationship can turn into a living nightmare when physical violence is added to mental abuse and insults. Physical violence is not just about battery, there are other forms of physical abuse in relationships besides beatings. In the physical violence it also involves (i) Pushing, shaking or throwing something at the partner (ii) slapping him or her, twisting of the arm, pulling the hair, kicking, dragging, beating, punching or hitting the partner with something harmful (iii) choking or burning a partner on purpose, threatening or attacking a partner with a weapon for instance gun or knife. Contrary to popular belief, physical abuse in relationships is a serious and widespread problem. It is also tragic and drastically changes lives (Effah-Chukwuma, Ukommi, and Bassey, 2022).

Sexual violence, on the other hand, is forced sexual intercourse- physically forcing a partner to perform any other sexual act when undesired and forcing her with threats to perform sexual acts without her consent. It is any sexual act or attempt to obtain a sexual act by violence or coercion act to traffic a person, or act directed against a person's sexuality, regardless of the relationship to the victim. It occurs in times of peace and armed conflict situations, it is widespread, and is considered to be one of the most traumatic, pervasive, and common human rights violations. Sexual violence is a serious public health problem and has a profound short and long-term impact on physical and mental health (Effah-Chukwuma, Ukommi, and Bassey, 2022). The last one would be emotional violence, which entails humiliating the partner in public, threatening to hurt or harm someone close to the partner's family, and finally insulting or making the partner feel bad about themselves. Since the beginning of time, countless individuals have endured unimaginable suffering in violent Intimate Partner relationships, especially in marriages. Many of them have stayed in these unions out of fear of being labelled as marital failures. Some do it for their kids' sake, while others do it because they do not believe in divorce or the lack of finances to move on. However, the scope of intimate partner violence has moved beyond violence against women in a romantic relationship to also cover violence against men in intimate relationships, although this is a rare occurrence (Coker, Davis, Arias, and Brandt, 2002). Even though there has been so much alarm about intimate partner violence against women across the globe, intimate partner violence against men is a reality. It occurs virtually in every society in varying degrees. The problems in conducting studies that seek to describe violence in terms of gender are the amount of silence, fear, and shame that result from abuse within families and relationships. This is why domestic violence against men remains largely unreported (Abayomi, 2014).

The Nigerian society is a highly patriarchal one, in which men have bloated egos and high self-esteem (Brown and Akpan, 2020). Though there is a prevalence of intimate partner

violence against women in Nigeria, as many women have died, been brutalized, or maimed for life by their violent male counterparts, however, there is also a prevalence of domestic violence against men, which has largely remained under-reported. The under-reporting of intimate partner violence, according to Abayomi (2014) is almost universal and may be due to the sensitive nature of the subject. Husband punching, slapping, kicking, nail scratching, sex deprivation, and killing are realities that occur in Nigeria. The tragedy is that men who find themselves in this situation hide and do not talk openly about their ugly experience, as talking about it will bruise their ego and expose them to ridicule in a male-dominated society. Brown and Akpan (2020) also found that familism and conformity to family loyalty, trust, integrity, unity, progress and defence of family values have induced an expansion on the spaces of crime and in some cases, result to homicide and intimate partner violence.

Several laws protect men and women alike, things have changed. We now live in a time where violence against a partner in an intimate relationship is considered a serious crime. Despite all the efforts and sensitization programs carried out by the different government parastatals, NGO's and human rights bodies, there are still cases of violence against women in intimate partner relationships. Intimate partner violence has been identified among some couples in Uyo municipality. Cases abound whereby some husbands maltreat their spouses, causing some of them to leave their marriages. Thereafter they might decide to remain unmarried and subsequently engage in sexual deviations such as masturbation, lesbianism, prostitution, to mention but a few while some may stay back in such relationships and engage in extramarital affairs, masturbation and bisexuality.

Sexual deviation, otherwise known as Paraphilia or sexual perversion is the experience of intense sexual arousal to atypical objects, situations, fantasies, behaviours or individuals. It has also been defined as sexual interest in anything other than a consenting human partner. It presents in form of lesbianism, masturbation, prostitution, total abstinence from sexual activities to mention but a few. While it has been frequently suggested that sexual deviations are learned, the learning has usually been thought of as taking place during one traumatic experience.

In Africa and Nigeria where culture exerts enormous influence that seems to affect women negatively, the rate of Intimate Partners Violence expectedly is alarmingly high. It is put at 36% (CDC, 2016). This is more than the global average. Considering the scanty nature of comprehensive statistics on IPV in Nigeria, one is left to his/her guesses. According to the data gathered by UNICEF on violent unions published on May 2022, in nearly half of 67 countries with available data, more than 1 in 5 ever-married adolescent girls have experienced physical and/or sexual violence by a husband or partner within the past year. These include countries spanning regions from Asia to sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America and the Caribbean, indicating that adolescent girls everywhere are exposed to this form of violence.

Akwa Ibom State is not left out as there have been cases of IPV between couples in intimate relationships in Uyo urban. According to a publication on business day dated 22nd of February 2022, a pastor in Eket, Akwa Ibom State reportedly killed his wife and buried her in a shallow grave in their rented apartment but was later apprehended by the police for the alleged murder of his wife. Another incident was reported to have happened in Ikot Ataku, Okon in Eket Local Government Area involved one Pastor Chris Enoch, the founder of

Omega Word Global Ministries, Enoch who has five children from his wife, Patience, he allegedly killed, hails from Ebonyi State. These are evidences that there are indeed cases of IPV in Uyo Urban. Bonomi, Lee, and Ludwin (2017) stressed through their findings that SD was a direct cause of Intimate Partner Violence without taking into consideration that IPV can equally lead to SD.

Since a woman's life is fundamentally shaped by her sexuality and woman's sexuality can be affected by a variety of things, including medical diseases, social- religious views, age, psychological problems, despair, mental stress, disbelief and an unfulfilling marriage, and verbal and physical abuse, violence against women can lead to the development of psychological diseases such as melancholy, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, phobias and panic attacks (Kassel, 2021). These issues can negatively impact the sexual functions, connection, orientation and options of couples. Thus, this research becomes necessary to find out if extramarital affair is actually one of the outcomes of intimate partner violence.

Statement of the Problem

Many human cultures have always operated sexual relationships that exist between the male and the female. In this situation, human males and females are ideally expected to subsist among themselves and procreate through heterosexual unions. In many contemporary societies in Africa and beyond, several strands of human sexual relationships have emerged even as many agitations exist on the legalization of these sexual relationships. Lesbianism and Bisexuality have gradually become common place in many human societies and their members advocate for social inclusion.

The causes of these sexual deviations are traceable to both biological and social factors. While some studies like Jamali (2016) believe that sexual deviation is genetically inherited, others like Kassel (2021) hold that it is a learned behaviour. The latter category draws credence from findings which proof that IPV like (physical abuse, sexual abuse and emotional abuse) may likely result to sexual deviation. (Heidi, 2022) found that women who experience regular sexual and physical abuse are most likely susceptible to becoming bisexuals thereby having sexual relationships with other women. A study conducted by Rust (2012) found that teenage girls who experience sexual abuse before the age of 9 finally grow up to become lesbians or at least bisexuals.

Consequently, the rising cases of masturbation and other solitary sexual experiences are largely an outcome of IPV as a coping mechanism. Sounders and Hills (2017) found that the majority of women who engage in masturbation resort to it as a coping strategy in other to survive the effects of IPV which they suffer. Many cases abound where women engage in masturbation in other to avoid the dangers and implications of extra marital affairs like the risk of contracting a sexually transmitted disease. Sexual deviations therefore have constituted a social problem in our society because it is a form of sexual relationship that defies cultural and religious norms. Incidents of extra marital affairs and other forms of sexual deviation have largely resulted to family instability, health challenges, marital phobias, questionable paternity and a host of other related problems. Sexual deviation is indeed a form of social problem that has attracted the attention of religious leaders, civil organization, academic researchers and even the government. If these cases are not arrested, there is a high tendency for an increase in the rate of problems that will emanate as a result of

sexual deviation. Sadly, most researchers on IPV tend to play down on the influence of IPV on SD, they do not consider what victims of IPV do after experiencing such abuse, what direction their sexual life takes and how they cope with IPV. Some research findings on the effect of IPV on victims have confirmed that they are affected negatively (Thompson, 2016) and that such effects borders on lack of trust, lack of self-confidence, depression, etc. Victims do not find it necessary to trust nor do things with the gender of the offenders. Thus, this research sets out to investigate extramarital as an outcome of intimate partners' violence among couples in selected areas in Uyo urban.

Objectives of the Study

This study set out to ascertain if Intimate Partner Violence can lead to extra marital affairs in Uyo Urban.

Review of Related Literature

Concept of Intimate Partner Violence

Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) is one of the most prevalent social problems in both high and low income societies. It is a situation in which a current or former spouse or partner in an intimate relationship becomes violent against the other spouse or partner (Cases, Cantero and Jose, 2011). IPV can take a number of forms, including physical, verbal emotional, economic abuse. The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines IPV as “any behaviour within an intimate relationship that causes physical, psychological or sexual harm to those in the relationship, including acts of physical aggression, sexual coercion, and psychological abuse and controlling behaviours.” IPV is sometimes referred to simply as battery, or as spouse or partner abuse. Intimate Partner Violence is committed by one of the people in an intimate relationship against the other person, and can take place in relationships or between former spouses or partners. In its broadest sense, domestic violence also involves violence against children, parents, or the elderly.

It can assume multiple forms, including physical, verbal emotional, economic, religious, reproductive, or sexual abuse. It can range from subtle, coercive forms to marital rape and other violent physical abuse, such as choking, beating, female genital mutilation, and acid throwing that may result in disfigurement or death, and includes the use of technology to harass, control, monitor, stalk or hack. Intimate partner murder includes stoning, bride burning, honour killing, and dowry death, which sometimes involves non-cohabitating family members. Worldwide, the victims of domestic violence are overwhelmingly women, and women tend to experience more severe forms of violence. Intimate partner violence is among the most underreported crimes worldwide for both men and women. In addition, due to social stigmas regarding male victimization, men face an increased likelihood of being overlooked by healthcare providers (Miller and McCaw, 2019).

IPV often occurs when the abuser believes that they are entitled to it, or that it is acceptable, justified, or unlikely to be reported. In abusive relationships, there may be a cycle of abuse during which tensions rise and an act of violence is committed, followed by a period of reconciliation and calm. The victims may be trapped in domestically violent situations through isolation, power and control, traumatic bonding to the abuser, cultural acceptance,

lack of financial resources, fear, and shame, or to protect children. As a result of abuse, victims may experience physical disabilities, dysregulated aggression, chronic health problems, mental illness, limited finances, and a poor ability to create healthy relationships. Victims may experience severe psychological disorders, such as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Coker, Davies, Arias and Brandt, 2002). Children who live in a household with violence often show psychological problems from an early age, such as avoidance, hyper-vigilance to threats and dysregulated aggression, which may contribute to vicarious traumatization (Miller, 2006).

The most extreme form of IPV is termed intimate terrorism, coercive controlling violence, or simply coercive control (Miller and McCaw, 2019). In such situations, one partner is systematically violent and controlling. This is generally perpetrated by men against women, and is the most likely of the types to require medical services and the use of a women's shelter. Resistance to intimate terrorism, which is a form of self defense, and is termed violent resistance, is usually conducted by women.

Studies on Intimate Partner Violence against Men suggest that men are less likely to report domestic violence perpetrated by their female intimate partners (Randle and Graham, 2011). Conversely, men are more likely to commit acts of severe domestic battery, and women are more likely to suffer serious injury as a result. The most common but less injurious form of intimate partner violence is situational couple violence (also known as situational violence), which is conducted by men and women nearly equally, and is more likely to occur among younger couples, including adolescents and those of college age (Finkel and Eckhardt, 2013). Intimate partner violence occurs between two people in an intimate relationship. It may occur between heterosexual or homosexual couples and victims can be male or female. Couples may be dating, cohabiting or married and violence can occur in or outside of the home. Studies showed that both men and women could be abusers or victims of domestic violence. Women are more likely to act violently in retaliation or self-defense and tend to engage in less severe forms of violence than men whereas men are more likely to commit long-term cycles of abuse than women.

The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines intimate partner violence as "any behaviour within an intimate relationship that causes physical, psychological or sexual harm to those in the relationship". According to a study conducted by WHO in 2013, 30% of women globally aged 15 and older have experienced physical and/or sexual intimate partner violence. Global estimates by WHO (2013) calculated that the incidence of women who had experienced physical or sexual abuse from an intimate partner in their lifetime was 1 in 3.

A study by Tjaden (2002) noted that women who were more likely to experience intimate partner violence had some common demographic factors. Women who had children by age 21 were twice as likely to be victims of intimate partner violence as women who were not mothers at that age. Men who had children by age 21 were more than three times as likely to be people who abuse compared to men who were not fathers at that age. Many male abusers are also substance abusers. Leonard and Quigley (2017) found that more than two-thirds of males who commit or attempt homicide against a partner used alcohol, drugs, or both during the incident; less than one-fourth of the victims did. The lower the household income, the higher the reported cases of intimate partner violence rates and vice versa (Leonard and Quigley, 2017). Intimate Partner Violence impairs a woman's capacity to find employment. A study of women who received social benefits found that domestic violence

was associated with a general pattern of reduced stability of employment.

The victims of one type of abuse are often the victims of other types of abuse. Severity tends to increase with multiple incidents, especially if the abuse comes in many forms. If the abuse is more severe, it is more likely to have chronic effects on victims because the long-term effects of abuse tend to be cumulative (Cases, Cantero and Jose, 2011). Because this type of violence is most likely to be extreme, survivors of intimate partner violence are most likely to require medical services and the safety of shelters. Consequences of physical or sexual intimate violence include chronic pain, gastrointestinal and gynecological problems, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, and death. Other mental health consequences are anxiety, substance abuse, and low-self-esteem (Cases, Cantero and Jose, 2011).

Sexual violence by intimate partners varies by country, with an estimated 15 million adolescent girls surviving forced sex worldwide. In some situations forced sex, or marital rape, often occurs with other forms of domestic violence, particularly physical abuse.

Some estimates show that as many as 50% of couples who experience IPV engage in some form of reciprocal violence (Sugg, 2015). Nevertheless, most services address offenders and survivors separately. In addition, many couples who have experienced IPV decide to stay together. In fact, 37-58% of couples who seek regular outpatient treatment have experienced physical assault in the past year (Sugg, 2015). In these cases, clinicians are faced with the decision as to whether they should accept or refuse to treat these couples. Although the use of conjoint treatment for IPV is controversial as it may present a danger to victims and potentially escalate abuse, it may be useful to others, such as couples experiencing situational couple violence. Scholars and practitioners in the field call for tailoring of interventions to various sub-types of violence and individuals served.

Prevalence and Trends in Intimate Partner Violence

Estimates published by the World Health Organization indicate that globally about 1 in 3 (30%) of women worldwide have been subjected to either physical and/or sexual intimate partner violence or non-partner sexual violence in their lifetime while 1 in every 25 men has suffered physical abuse by their female partner (WHO, 2013). Worldwide, almost one-third (27%) of women aged 15-49 years who have been in a relationship report that they have been subjected to some form of physical and/or sexual violence by their intimate partner. Violence can negatively affect women's physical, mental, sexual, and reproductive health, and may increase the risk of acquiring HIV in some settings. The health sector has an important role to play to provide comprehensive health care to victims subjected to intimate partner violence, and as an entry point for referring women to other support services they may need. Over a quarter of women aged 15-49 years who have been in a relationship have been subjected to physical and/or sexual violence by their intimate partner at least once in their lifetime (since age 15). The prevalence estimates of lifetime intimate partner violence range from 20% in the Western Pacific, 22% in high-income countries and Europe and 25% in the Regions of the Americas to 33% in the African region, 31% in the Eastern Mediterranean region, and 33% in the South-East Asia region (WHO, 2013). Globally, as many as 38% of all murders of women are committed by intimate partners in addition to intimate partner violence, globally 6% of women report having been sexually assaulted by someone other than a partner, although data for non-partner sexual violence are more limited

(WHO, 2013). Intimate partner and sexual violence are mostly perpetrated by men against women.

Walker (1979) in a study, interviewed 1,500 women who had been subject to intimate partner violence and found that there was a similar pattern of abuse, called the "cycle of abuse". In the study, it was found that intimate partner abuse usually follows four cyclical stages: tension, incident, reconciliation, and calm. During the tension stage, the abusive partner may begin to display signs of abuse and behaviours that slowly increase in intensity and frequency. This may be related to external stressors like financial difficulties, interpersonal challenges at work or other environments, or health challenges. The increasingly tense behaviours can include: emotional outbursts, irritability, impatience, shortness of temper. As the tension starts to become evident, the non-abusive partner may also feel increasingly anxious. This may lead them to act in specific ways — such as “walking on eggshells” — to ease and appease the abusive partner's tension and prevent an abusive incident.

After the incident of abuse, the abusive partner may feel like the tension starts to dissipate. This can be quite the opposite experience for the person who's on the receiving end of that abuse. Once that tension has abated, they may feel inclined to make amends for their behaviour. They may apologize, shower you with affection, or promise they will never do it again. During this phase, the abusive partner may seem genuinely ashamed of their behaviour and committed to reform. Because you care about them, you may feel inclined to believe what they are saying and give them another chance. It is possible that the abusive partner starts doing things that may seem romantic, supportive, and loving during the reconciliation stage.

During the calm phase, the abusive partner may continue to be attentive; however, one might notice a shift from them being apologetic to now excusing their actions. During the calm stage, abusive behaviours may be minimized. The abusive partner will shift responsibility for the abuse, justifies their behaviour. This stage can feel confusing. The abusive partner seemed to want to make things right, but there is now an underlying tone of dismissal. After a while, the abusive partner may start experiencing tension again, as the cycle of abuse starts once more.

In general, intimate partner violence may involve sexual, sadistic control, economic physical, emotional and psychological abuse. The victims of one type of abuse are often the victims of other types of abuse. Severity tends to increase with multiple incidents, especially if the abuse comes in many forms. If the abuse is more severe, it is more likely to have chronic effects on victims because the long-term effects of abuse tend to be cumulative. Because this type of violence is most likely to be extreme, survivors of intimate violence are most likely to require medical services and the safety of shelters. Consequences of physical or sexual intimate partner violence include chronic pain, gastrointestinal and gynecological problems, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, and death. Other mental health consequences are anxiety, substance abuse, and low self-esteem. Abusers are more likely to have witnessed abuse as children than those who engage in situational couple violence.

While both women and men can be victims and perpetrators of IPV, the majority of such violence is inflicted upon women, who are also much more likely to suffer injuries as a result, in both heterosexual and same-sex relationships. Although men and women commit equivalent rates of unreported minor violence via situational altercation, more severe

perpetration and domestic battery tends to be committed by men (Jewkes, 2002). A 2014 systematic review published in *Journal of Violence and Victims* found that despite less serious altercation or violence being equal among both men and women, more serious and violent abuse was perpetrated by men. It was also found that women's use of physical violence was more likely motivated by self-defense or fear whereas men's use of violence was motivated by control (Finneran and Stephenson, 2014). A 2011 systematic review published in the *Journal of Family Violence* found that the common motives for female on male IPV were anger, a need for attention, or as a response to their partner's violence (Garrido, Culhan, Petrenko and Taussig, 2011). A 2011 review published in the *Journal of Aggression and Violent Behaviour* found differences in the methods of abuse employed by men and women, suggesting that men were more likely to beat up, choke or strangle their partners, whereas women were more likely to throw something at their partner, slap, kick, bite, punch, or hit with an object (Johnson, 2011).

Women generally suffer more severe and long-lasting forms of partner abuse than men, and men generally have more opportunities to leave an abusive partner than women do. Researchers have found different outcomes in men and women in response to such abuse. A 2012 review from the *Journal of Marital and Family Therapy* found that women suffered from over-proportionate numbers of injuries, fear, and post-traumatic stress as a result of partner violence (Olson, Russell, Kessler and Miller, 2012). The review also found that 70% of female victims felt frightened as a result of violence perpetrated by their partners whereas 85% of male victims expressed "no fear" in response to such violence. IPV correlated with relationship satisfaction for women but it did not do so for men (Olson, Russell, Kessler and Miller, 2012).

The UN Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women (DEVW), defines the term "violence against women" means any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual, or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or private life. Usually, acts of violence against women are measured in three dimensions physical, emotional, and sexual violence. Globally, the most common form of violence against women is executed by a husband or other close partners (85%). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), domestic violence, mainly intimate partner violence, has a significant component of gender-based violence. Intimate personal violence refers to any behavior within an intimate relationship that causes physical, psychological, or sexual harm to those in the relationship. Thirty percent of women aged 15 and above have experienced physical and sexual violence by their partners in the world. Whereas, seven percent of women have encountered sexual violence by non-partners 27.5 percent of women were with physical and emotional violence (WHO, 2013).

In Europe, 20% of women have been a victim of physical or sexual intimate partner violence whereas both physical and emotional violence was experienced by 22.5% of the women. About 9.6% of women in the study encountered sexual violence, indicating that physical and emotional violence has taken the lead followed by physical and emotional violence was encountered by 22.5% of women, while sexual violence was 9.6% of women. This indicates that physical and emotional violence is predominant. The proportion of ever-partnered women who had ever suffered physical violence by a male intimate partner ranged from 13% in Africa to 61% in Nigeria, with most sites falling between 23 and 49% while the

range of lifetime prevalence of physical or sexual violence, or both, by an intimate partner was 15–71%, with estimates in most sites ranging from 30 to 60% and women in the Japan being the least likely to have ever experienced physical or sexual violence, or both, by an intimate partner (WHO, 2013).

Intimate Partner Violence has a significant impact on the empowerment of women. Compared to women who have not experienced intimate partner violence, women who have experienced intimate partner violence are feeling discouraged and hopeless. The most common foundation of physical, psychological, and emotional morbidity of women is because of unavoidable violence against them. There are numerous forms of intimate partner violence. The three acts of intimate partner violence such as physical, emotional, and sexual violence have been associated with health concerns including sexual, physical, reproductive health, behavioral and psychological problems. Commonly, emotional violence against women is an intrinsic aspect of both physical and sexual violence against women. A study conducted in the United Kingdom revealed a considerable coexistence between physical, emotional, and sexual violence (Sounders and Hills, 2017). The findings of the study also captured that a high prevalence of intimate partner violence, in particular, emotional violence is the prevalent violence. More than half of women were victims of emotional, physical, and or sexual violence at least once by their husbands, and 45.3% gave a history of persistent abuse (Sounders and Hills, 2017). Though gender-based violence is a global health problem, it is higher in developing countries in Africa. As a result of traditional, religious, and others factors in the communities, the highest proportion of intimate partner violence is existed in Africa (WHO, 2013). Women living in Eastern and Western African regions experience the highest levels of gender-based violence. A study involving the 2016 Ugandan Demographic and Health Survey showed that still a high prevalence of domestic violence in the form of physical, emotional, or sexual violence against women from an intimate partner (Kaggwa, Kule and Nkola, 2021). Community-based studies on pregnant women reported that the prevalence of domestic violence ranged from 32.2 to 45.5 percent. Besides, 25.4 percent overall prevalence of domestic violence such as physical, emotional, and sexual violence was 8.1, 24.5, and 2.4% respectively in Kampala, Kira and Mbarara in Uganda. Almost one-third of Ugandan women aged 15–49 experienced at least one type of violence in their lifetime and one-third of women globally (Kaggwa, Kule and Nkola, 2021).

A study in Northern Nigeria revealed that almost sixteen percent of female university students experienced one or more gender-based violence committed. In particular, students experienced physical (22.8%), sexual (22.2%), and emotional violence (50.8%). In this study, it is also reported that almost thirty percent of students were exposed to pressure by their teachers for sex, and eighteen percent were usually harassed by their classmates (Giordano, Mackenzie, Longmore and Manning, 2022). A study in the United Kingdom found that intimate personal violence in developing countries is high (Sugg, 2015). However, often it is difficult to identify women at risk because of a culture of silence within the countries. Though the Universal Declaration of Human Rights declares that all people need to be recognized irrespective of gender, women have continued to suffer from intimate partner violence. The Declaration tried to investigate in different periods to determine the recent trends of prevalence of intimate partner violence. However, due to cultural and other restrictions, the government leads to giving less attention. African countries have taken the highest proportion including the largest populist country in the continent, Nigeria.

The Nigerian community is a masculine community that considers husbands' ability over women in the household which aggravates the occurrence of violence against women. Numerous studies have been done on the causes of physical, emotional, and sexual violence against women such as socioeconomic and demographic determinants. Little attention was given to a comprehensive study that assesses the association between physical, emotional, and sexual violence against women in Nigeria as well.

Intimate Partner Violence and Extra Marital Affairs

There is growing evidence that intimate partner violence influences other sexual deviant behavior like extramarital affairs (Sounders and Hills, 2017). Physical abuse could have the ability to predict sexual functioning in women as it can worsen sexual functioning dimensions among women victims of IPV. Extramarital sex occurs when a married person engages in sexual activity with someone other than their spouse. The term may be applied to the situation of a single person having sex with a married person. Where extramarital sexual relations do breach a sexual norm, it may be referred to as adultery (sexual acts between a married person and a person other than the spouse), or infidelity. These terms imply moral or religious consequences, whether in civil law or religious law (Johan, Sayeed, Raham and Zara, 2017).

Kinsey (2015) found 50% of American males and 26% of females had extramarital sex. It was estimated that 26–50% of men and 21–38% of women or 22.7% of men and 11.6% of women had extramarital sex and more than half of the women who admitted extramarital sex justified that on the grounds of emotional abuse from their husbands. Durex's Global Sex Survey (2005) found that 44% of adults worldwide reported having had one-night extramarital sex and 22% had an affair. In the United States, 16% of married partners have had extramarital sex, nearly twice as many men as women, while an additional 30% have fantasized about extramarital sex. Reasons for indulgence revealed low sexual performance and intimate partner abuse by spouses (Kinsey, 2015). A 2016 study by the Institute for Family Studies in the US found that black Protestants had a higher rate of extramarital sex than Catholics. Jones (2018), in a US study found that 53.5% of Americans who admitted having extramarital sex did so with someone they knew well, such as a close friend. About 29.4% were with someone who's somewhat well-known, such as a neighbour, co-worker or long-term acquaintance, and the rest were with casual acquaintances. The study also found some gender differences, such as that men are more likely than women to hold more favourable attitudes about extramarital sex, and that among those who reported having extramarital sex in the past year, about 12% of men had paid for sex compared to 1% for women. Engagement in extramarital sex has been associated with individuals who have a higher libido (sex drive) than their partner in addition to intimate partner violence. The rise of technology and universal access to the internet/smartphones has led to effortless engagement with texting, chat lines, pornography, dating websites for the married and easy access to individuals working in prostitution. Therapeutic intervention for sex addiction has become a growing industry, while the call to personal responsibility and accountability is constantly diminishing. These avenues allow for easy sharing of experiences on intimate partner violence which likely results in extramarital affairs.

Reducing infidelity to sexual incompatibility or relationship issues and labeling ongoing extra-marital sexual relations as sex addiction - a sickness to be treated - ignores the fact that infidelity itself is abuse and ignores the role that IPV plays in a larger pattern of

infidelity (Bazyar, Jamil, and Sadegh, 2021). Inherent in the act of infidelity is chronic lying, scheming, manipulation, blame shifting and duplicity which are all psychological patterns of abusive behaviour. This behaviour also knowingly takes away the faithful partner's right to make decisions around their sexual health or actively practice safe sex.

Theoretical Framework

Differential Association Theory

This theory was developed by Edwin Sutherland in 1966 and it proposes that through interaction with others, individuals learn the values, attitudes, techniques, and motives for criminal behaviour. This theory focuses on how individuals learn to become deviants, but does not concern itself with why they become deviants. By this, individuals learn how to commit deviant acts; they learn motives, drives, rationalizations and attitudes. It grows socially easier for the individuals to commit a crime. Sutherland argues that people become delinquent due to an excess of contacts with delinquent patterns and isolation from non-delinquent behaviours. Their inspiration is the processes of cultural transmission and construction. Differential association predicts that an individual will choose the criminal path when the balance of definitions for law-breaking exceeds those for law-abiding. This tendency will be reinforced if social association provides active people in the person's life. The principles of Sutherland's Theory of Differential Association are as follows: deviant behaviour is learned from other individuals, deviant behaviour is learned in interaction with other persons in a process of communication, the principle part of the learning of deviant behaviour occurs within intimate personal groups. When criminal behaviour is learned, the learning includes (a) techniques of committing the crime, which are sometimes very complicated, sometimes simple; (b) the specific direction of motives, drives, rationalizations, and attitudes.

Applying the theory of differential association to this study, the theory projects that extramarital affairs, masturbation and bisexuality are more of learned behaviour and practices than inherited traits. It assumes that victims of intimate partner violence learn to adopt these forms of sexual deviation as a coping strategy due to a series of consistent abuse by their partners. Practicing these sexual behaviours therefore, is learned during the process of socialization from friends, acquaintances or the media. This study will therefore justify or refute the postulations of this theory in the study area.

Methodology

The survey research method was adopted for this study. Survey research is the process of conducting research using a selected or defined population (Visser, Krosnick and Lavrakas, 2000). This method involves the use of interview schedules, focus group discussions and key informant interview on a certain population. This method was considered suitable for the study because the subject of this research cuts across different segments of people in the society, hence the justification for its adoption. Data for this study were drawn from those who have experienced any form of intimate partner violence. The study therefore was based on both male and female individuals who have had past or current experiences of abuse from their intimate partner.

The area of this study was Uyo Urban. Participants in the study were drawn within the geographical boundaries of Uyo Urban area. Uyo Urban constitutes areas covering Uyo

Local Government and major areas like Aka Road, Nwaniba, Ewet Housing Estate, Abak Road, Barracks Road, Ikot Ekpene Road, Oron Road and the University of Uyo Town Campus Area. Uyo Urban boast of several infrastructural facilities like Ibom Tropicana, the E-library, Godswill Akpabio International Stadium, etc.

The population of this study constituted mainly women above the age of 18 who had experienced at least one form of intimate partner violence either from their previous or current intimate relationship. However two men were utilized as key informants to enable the researcher elicit the necessary data from the point of view of gender consciousness. The sample of this study was 120 respondents (115 participants and 5 key informants). This was attained through a saturation process where the researcher gathered data from as many participants as possible until the responses reached a saturation point. The sampling technique of this study was based on non-probability sampling methods. The purposive and the snowball sampling techniques were adopted in the selection of participants for the study. While the purposive sampling technique was used in recruiting key informants, a combination of the snowball and purposive sampling techniques was used in recruiting participants for in-depth interview and focus group discussion respectively.

The purposive sampling was adopted for this study. It is non-probability sampling technique in which the sampling members are chosen only on the basis of the researcher's knowledge and judgment. As the researcher's knowledge is instrumental and primary in this sampling process, there are chances that the results obtained will be lightly accurate with a minimum of error. This was chosen because the researcher intentionally went for those members in the study area who have experienced any form of IPV.

In addition, the snowball sampling was also adopted in the study. It is a non-probability sampling technique in which the samples provide referrals to recruit other samples required for a research study. This sampling technique can go on and on just as the snowball increases in size, in this case the sample size, till when the researcher has enough data to analysis and draw conclusions. In this study, the Human Right Commission, Directorate of Social Welfare as well as Brighter Hope Initiative were consulted for information relating to intimate partner violence and its victims in Uyo Urban. Through these organizations, contacts were established with victims of intimate partner violence and the interview sessions and FGDs took place.

The interview guide was used as one of the instruments for eliciting data from participants via in-depth interviews, key informant interviews and focused group discussions. In addition, oral interviews were applied in many cases to further buttress the content of the interview guide. Data collected for this study were analysed qualitatively.

Results

Have you engaged in extra-marital affairs/have you cheated on your partner before? If yes, what led to it?

On this, a 30-year old married woman confides thus:

“Yes, I have but sometimes I regret it and at another times, I'm proud of my actions. The first time I ever cheated on my husband was because of the way he slaps and beats me. I was always so frustrated so I needed something to distract me from him” **(Business woman;**

married)

Another participant shares the following experience:

“I have, even up till now. I never believed that I would be so happy doing this. My husband is a chronic cheat and when I confront him, he abuses me violently so I concluded to date another man too” **(38 years old; married women, civil servant)**

Another participant brings this to bear:

“Yes, I even have a BF (boyfriend). One major reason that drove my heart to another was his constant abuse of me. He beats me up at will and at every little provocation. So, when this person came, he treated me better, differently and I gave him my heart and my body” **years old married woman, trader).**

Did you cheat with a man, or another woman?

A participant shares thus:

“For me, both o! I have fun with both men and women alike and I'm okay” **(22 years, single student)**

37-year old woman shares as follows:

“I have never done women before o! But when I started it, it was not bad. Men are too full of heartbreaks and disappointments but women are more reliable” **(Female; public servant)**

Another participant adds thus:

“I do it with females; women are more dependable than men. Let me endure that unfaithful one (my husband) in the house. After all, he caused me to do this? **(32 years old; business woman)**

Do your friends or partner know about your sexual relations?

A participant shares thus:

“God forbid! How will they know? Nobody in my family knows it. It's a secret between me and my very close friends”. **(29 years old; married woman; business owner)**

Another participant expresses her thought:

“No need for family to know. After all, I don't know everything about him (my husband). But my girlfriends know; almost all my close friends because we run it together”. **(34-year old married woman; civil servant)**

Discussion of Findings

As a coping mechanism therefore, these manifested expressions of intimate partner violence mostly suffered by women have gradually resulted in some forms of sexual deviation as found in the study area. Although, these sexual acts are socially proscribed by the vast majority of residents in the study area, these supposed victims engage in them as a coping mechanism for IPV they suffer in their intimate relationships. These findings are largely in contravention with popular opinion that sexual deviations triggers intimate partner violence. In this case, study has shown that there exist a plethora of sexual deviant involvements (extramarital affairs, masturbation and bi-sexuality) that are caused by intimate partner violence. This study shows that most practitioners of these sexual deviant acts do so as a way to achieve sexual desires which have largely been bashed due to a recurrence of violent attacks by their intimate partner.

It was found that the prevalence of IPV in the study area stands at an average of 4-5 officially reported cases in the study area monthly and about an average of 60 officially recorded cases yearly for the past five years and this is alarmingly very disturbing. This is however comparatively low in comparison with the findings of Coston (2021) who submitted that the prevalence of IPV in Massachusetts stands at an average of 9 cases monthly and over 500 officially recorded IPV cases in the past five years.

In addition, study found that intimate partner violence has resulted in extramarital affairs as some female victims of IPV engage in extramarital sexual activities as a coping strategy to alley their emotional and psychological abuse. This finding is consistent with that of Sounders and Hills (2017) who found that women who suffer intimate partner violence on a regular basis can most likely engage in an extramarital affair as a way of relieving their pains incurred during the violent attack.

Conclusion

This study has obviously brought to the fore that intimate partner violence can trigger deviant sexual acts like extramarital sex, masturbation and bisexuality. The study clearly showed that the consequence of IPV cuts beyond physical and emotional consequences and penetrates into sexual deviant behaviours. The study clearly established that victims in Uyo urban engaged in extra-marital affairs as means of gaining or achieving sexual satisfaction which no longer gotten from their partners as expected. In addition to the findings of other studies, this study further confirms that women are the most vulnerable group in cases of IPV than men and most of these violent incidents among intimate partners are triggered by infidelity, economics amongst other factors.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made by the researchers:

- (i) Victims of IPV should be encouraged to speak-up and report their violent experiences for appropriate sanctions and necessary action on the culpable perpetrator.
- (ii) The Nigerian justice system should consider IPV as a more serious offence and as such, promulgate more stringent sanctions against offenders. If this is done, it will encourage other latent victims to report their abusers.
- (iii) Partners should be enlighten on the dangers of IPV especially in the aspect of sexual deviant behaviours which lead to extra-marital affairs.

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